

WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN POLICE

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Abstract: Today in the fast-running phase of life, people really find it difficult to manage a balance between the pressure of work place and the duties of a home- maker, be it a male or female. “Work- family balance” evolved into “work –life balance” partly in response to workers which means the working women should have a balance between work and life to take care of their responsibilities too. The present study was undertaken to determine the work life balance and analyses the problems faced by women police. The women police personnel most of the time work under stress due to work load, extended duty hours, political pressures, personal or family problems etc. Police put up with long and irregular working hours without any break i.e.; 24x 7 duties. Then the women in police force have to do both the roles in office and home. The study is conducted in Malappuram District and a sample of 55 women police were selected by using purposive sampling method. The study also measures the job satisfaction experienced by women police.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Women Police, Job Stress, Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The present study is an attempt to know the work life balance experienced by women in police. Work Life Balance refers to an individual’s ability to balance the commitments and goals relating to their paid work with the personal commitments, responsibilities at work and at home. The work load of a police compared with other employees is quite demanding. Police work is very tough, exhausting and complicated. Under certain conditions the police have to work 24*7 hours, irregular working schedule, controlling public and dealing with criminals. Women police due to excessive work load are not able to maintain a proper balance between their personal life and work. Major obstacle for police women is uncertain time limit, insufficient working conditions and expected to work in masculinised style.

II. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Today working Women in India is continually challenged by the demands of full-time work. They carry more of the responsibilities and commitments. Though there are studies on work life balance, relatively there are fewer on women police. In comparison with men, women have more responsibilities at home. So, they want work life balance which refers to relationship between work and family. The women police personnel most of the time work under stress due to work load, extended duty hours, family problem etc. Due to the nature of job they have to work overtime, they may require to work in an unfavourable situation, they may face political pressure under certain situations, etc. All these will lead to job stress and poor work life balance among women police. The women in police force have to do both the roles in office and home. Hence there is a need to study how women are balancing their work and family life in police force.

III. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study is limited to women police in Malappuram district. The study covers important areas like work life balance problems of employees, level of satisfaction with Work life balance, the factors influencing work life balance of

employees, etc. The career for women is continuously challenged by the increasing demands at work place. Socio-economic characteristics of respondents were considered for the purpose of study to measure job satisfaction and job stress.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To analyze the factors influencing work life balance of women police.
2. To measure the level of job satisfaction and job stress of women police.
3. To identify and analyze the problem faced by women police.

V. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no association between age and work life balance of women police.
2. There is no association between type of family and work life balance of women police.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population of the study constitutes the women police in Malappuram district. The sample size of the study is 55. They are selected by using purposive sampling. Both primary and secondary data are used for the study. Primary data is collected from women police in Malappuram District and secondary data from books, journals and internet. Questionnaire method is used for collecting data. The statistical tools such as percentage, ranking, scaling etc are used for data analysis. Graphs are also used to have more clarity.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Factors influencing work life balance

Factors	Mean score
Age	3.545
Family Support	6.8
Work Environment	6.47
Training Programme	4.2
Relocation/Transfer	3.38
Recreational Facilities provided	3.47
Benefits awarded	3.95
Dependent care	4.18

From this analysis we can understand that family support is the most important factor influencing work life balance (mean score of 6.8). The second factor is work environment (mean score 6.47) and third factor is training programme given by the authorities (mean score 4.2). The least influenced factors are recreational facilities provided, relocation or transfer and benefits awarded.

Table 2: Level of job stress

Level	Percentage
High	45%
Medium	24%
Low	31%

Nearly half of the respondents are experiencing high level of stress (45%). Only 31% respondents are experiencing low level of stress.

Table 3: Level of Job satisfaction on various factors

Factors	Level of Satisfaction				
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Working Hours	0	37	11	5	2
Working Environment	2	40	13	0	0
Recreational facilities	1	29	14	10	1
Medical facility	3	30	15	5	2
Food And Refreshment	2	30	17	6	0
Leave Facility	1	27	18	8	1
Transfer Facility	1	33	14	7	0
Accommodation Facility	2	38	10	5	0
Dependent Care	3	20	22	10	0
Family Support	18	34	2	1	0
Support From Colleagues	16	25	12	1	1
Support From Superiors	10	29	15	1	0

This analysis shows that a greater number of respondents are satisfied with three factors such as work environment, family support and support from colleagues. More number of respondents are dissatisfied with dependent care. To conclude, most of the respondents are satisfied with all the factors influencing work life balance.

Table 4: Problems contributing to work life imbalances

Problems	Frequency
Excessive work load	32
Frequent transfer	4
Job related stress	38
Lack of support from colleagues	16
Lack of support from family	6
Excessive household work	24
Family issues	10
Workplace issues	11

The above analysis reveals that job related stress and excessive work load are the two important problems that contribute work life imbalance among women police. The next problem is excessive household work. The least problems that contribute to work life imbalance are frequent transfer, lack of support from family, work place issues, and family issues.

Table 5: Overall work life balance of women police

Work life balance	Percentage
Very good	4%
Good	36%
Average	54%
Poor	6%
Very poor	0

This analysis shows that most of the respondents are able to maintain an average work life balance (54%). 36% respondents opinioned that they are able to maintain a good work life balance and 4% are maintaining a very good work life balance.

Table 6: Results of Hypotheses Testing

Null Hypotheses	Test	Table Value	Chi-square Value	Result
There is no association between age and work life balance of women police.	Chi-Square Test	15.507	9.2768	Ho accepted at 5%
There is no association between type of family and work life balance of women police.	Chi-Square Test	9.488	1.5276	Ho accepted at 5%

The chi-square analysis reveals that there is no significant association between age and work life balance and also no significant association between type of family and work life balance of women police.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The present study identified the factors influencing work life balance of women police. The most influenced factors are family support and work environments. The least influenced factors are recreational facilities, benefits; transfer etc. Job related stress and excessive work load are the two important problems that contributes to work life imbalance among women police. Most of the women police are experiencing a high level of stress. The study concluded that most of the women police are able to maintain average work life balance and they are satisfied with their job and work life balance they maintain.

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